

YASHIL

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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Elektron nashr. 815 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-mayda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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TOURISM AND REGIONAL IDENTITY IN UZBEKISTAN: BALANCING HERITAGE AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article investigates the complicated relationship between tourism development and regional identity in Uzbekistan. As the country develops into one of the main cultural tourism destinations in Central Asia, it is of concern how tourism may impact local customs, values, and social cohesion. The research involved included interviews with local peoples, community arts groups, and tourism professionals, was aimed to investigate how the tourism sector frames, distorts, and sustained regional identity.

Key words: tourism development, local identity, cultural heritage, silk road cities, sustainable tourism, tourist perceptions, community involvement.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola O'zbekistonda turizm rivojlanishi va mintaqaviy o'ziga xoslik o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni o'rganadi. Mamlakat Markaziy Osiyodagi asosiy madaniy turizm yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylanar ekan, turizmning mahalliy urf-odatlar, qadriyatlar va ijtimoiy hamjihatlikka qanday ta'sir qilishi xavotirga solmoqda. Tadqiqotda turizm qanday qilib madaniyatni tovarga aylantirish yoki buzish orqali saqlab turishi va qayta shakllantirishi mumkinligini ko'rib chiqdi. Tadqiqot mahalliy xalqlar, jamoat san'at guruhlari va turizm mutaxassislari bilan intervyularni o'z ichiga olgan bo'lib, turizm sektori mintaqaviy o'ziga xoslikni qanday shakllantirishi, buzib ko'rsatishi va barqarorligini o'rganishga qaratilgan edi.

Kalit so'zlar: turizmni rivojlantirish, mahalliy o'ziga xoslik, madaniy meros, Ipak yo'li shaharlari, barqaror turizm, turistlik tasavvurlar, jamoatchilik ishtiroki.

Аннотация: В этой статье исследуется сложная взаимосвязь между развитием туризма и региональной идентичностью в Узбекистане. Поскольку страна превращается в одно из главных направлений культурного туризма в Центральной Азии, возникает вопрос, как туризм может повлиять на местные обычаи, ценности и социальную сплоченность. В исследование были включены интервью с местными жителями, общественными художественными группами и специалистами по туризму, и оно было направлено на изучение того, как туристический сектор формирует, искажает и поддерживает региональную идентичность.

Ключевые слова: развитие туризма, местная идентичность, культурное наследие, города Шелкового пути, устойчивый туризм, восприятие туристов, участие сообщества.

INTRODUCTION

Located in the center of Asia, Uzbekistan is a surprising gem that tourists from all over the world are eager to discover. With its breathtaking architecture, deep social history, and breathtaking natural beauty, Uzbekistan has the potential to become a major travel destination. However, the nation's travel business has faced a number of challenges, such as a lack of promotion, a lack of adequate infrastructure, and limited access to data. Despite these challenges, the Uzbek government has been actively promoting the travel sector because it recognizes its potential to boost economic growth, create jobs, and provide social protection. This page will include information on Uzbekistan's growing tourist and cultural sectors. [1]

According to another local researcher K.Egamnazarov, Uzbekistan's Silk Road cities are among the most alluring travel destinations in the world because of their warm hospitality, assortment of distinctive ancient structures, and the way of life and customs of the residents. [2] The study looked into how travelers saw the overall allure of Silk Road cities as well as the significance of the features that make a place appealing to visitors. In order to provide a current perspective on foreign tourists' opinions of Uzbekistan, this study aims to examine the destination attractiveness of Silk Road cities—Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva—from the viewpoints of both domestic and foreign tourists. The data gathered for this thesis is examined using a descriptive analysis. The results indicate that all cities' destinations are averagely attractive; no construct mean produced exceptional or unsatisfactory outcomes across the board. Despite the narrow scope of this study, the results indicate that Silk Road tourism has not yet reached its full potential. Additionally, research contributes to the body of knowledge regarding the perceptions and preferences of tourists from particular geographic origins toward the Central Asian nation, notably Uzbekistan, in terms of tourism products.

The tourism business in Uzbekistan has been gradually developing in recent years, and cuisine culture and culinary art are essential components of the country's heritage. However, there is a lack of detailed study on the significance of Tourism and Local Identity in Uzbekistan for boosting tourism in Uzbekistan. This research attempts to fill this gap and provide insights into how these factors might be used to further develop the tourism business in the country and what kind of factors plays an essential role for increased tourism in Uzbekistan.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Cultural identity is understood as the collective self-perception of a community, encompassing shared traditions, language, practices, and values [3]. In the context of globalization, tourism acts as a major force that both exposes and reshapes local identities. MacCannell introduced the concept of "staged authenticity," describing how cultural performances are modified for tourist consumption, often resulting in the simplification or commercialization of traditions. [4] Researcher like Kahraman and Cifci observed that, in the context of small island destinations—specifically, the Princes' Islands in Turkey—this study investigates the relationship between self-identification, memorable travel experiences, general satisfaction, and destination loyalty. [5] The authors used PLS-SEM to examine the relationship between self-identification and visitor experiences and loyalty, utilizing social identity theory and a quantitative methodology with 335 usable questionnaires. The findings indicate that memorable travel experiences operate as a mediator between self-identification and memorable experiences, contentment, and loyalty. on addition to offering useful advice for legislators and tourism planners on tiny island destinations, the study adds to our understanding of tourist behavior from a self-identity perspective. This study is noteworthy since it is the first to offer a comprehensive structural model that links these four important ideas in travel behavior.

Tourism can simultaneously serve as a tool for cultural revival and an agent of cultural distortion. Richards argues that while cultural tourism has contributed to renewed interest in heritage, it often risks transforming living traditions into commodified products. [6] The challenge for many destinations, including Uzbekistan, is to manage this tension between celebrating and preserving cultural heritage while catering to the expectations of a global tourist audience.

Few research has looked into the process of residents' value co-creation, despite the fact that it is essential for sustainable development and cultural preservation in the ethnic tourism community. In order to close this gap, this study uses the latent-moderated structural equations approach to test the relationships between place identity, mediators (interaction attitude, responsibility, and innovation attitude), spontaneous culture conservation, and self-efficacy moderators. The findings indicate a positive relationship between spontaneous culture conservation and place identification. Specifically, the impact of place identity on spontaneous culture conservation is mediated only by an attitude of responsibility and inventiveness. Furthermore, through accountability and an innovative mindset, self-efficacy mitigates the indirect impact of place identity on spontaneous culture conservation. These results support the sustainable growth of ethnic tourism communities and shed light on the mechanism of inhabitants' value co-creation. [7]

Uzbekistan's context: emerging research

While global literature on tourism and identity is extensive, research specific to Uzbekistan remains relatively limited but growing.

S.Timur studied tourism's economic effects in Samarkand and Bukhara, noting that while financial gains were evident, concerns about cultural homogenization and tourist-oriented modifications of traditional sites persisted. [8] M.Khalikov explored the transformation of handicrafts in Khiva, identifying a trend toward mass production of souvenirs targeted at tourists, often at the expense of authenticity. [9]

Recent government strategies, such as the "Silk Road Tourism Development Concept," aim to promote Uzbekistan's cultural assets internationally. [10] However, the focus tends to emphasize infrastructure and marketing, with less attention to potential impacts on living traditions and community identity.

There is also a notable absence of large-scale empirical studies assessing local community perceptions regarding how tourism affects their sense of identity and belonging. Addressing this gap is critical for designing culturally sensitive tourism policies. Marien André points out that developing the "Europe" brand internationally has become a major priority, particularly since tourism was officially recognized as an EU competency by the Lisbon Treaty. [11] [12] With a focus on competitiveness, the sharing of best practices, integrated strategies, and policy coherence, the EU currently seeks to promote and coordinate tourism across its member states. In response, the European Commission put up a new framework for tourism in 2010 that prioritized sustainability, innovation, and enhancing Europe's reputation abroad. André highlights that quality, sustainability, accessibility, and inclusivity should be given top priority in future European travel.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs both methods a qualitative and quantitative mixed-methods approach to examine the relationship between tourism and local identity in Uzbekistan. The main aim is to understand how tourism affects cultural expression, local perceptions, and identity formation in key touristic destinations such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva and other regions. Both primary and secondary data were utilized to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the research problem.

Data collection

Data collection will involve several methods to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The methods will be designed to capture both qualitative and quantitative data. Primary data was collected with a help of an online survey using Google Forms with a help of 22 questions and one of them open-ended question. The questionnaire was designed to gather demographic information such as age and location, status, travel habits, perceptions of local identity, and the impact of tourism on cultural traditions. The survey included both closed-ended like a multiple choice, Likert-scale and open-ended questions to allow for statistical analysis as well as in-depth insight into personal experiences and opinions.

The survey was distributed online with social media platforms and messaging apps, making it accessible to a broad audience across Uzbekistan. A total of 50 valid responses were collected. The participants represented diverse age groups and locations, providing a balanced sample for analysis. Moreover, the main attention was paid to the representation of individuals from tourism-heavy areas such as Samarkand, which had the highest number of participants.

The findings from qualitative and quantitative analyses will be integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. This will involve comparing and contrasting results from different data sources to draw meaningful conclusions about the role of Tourism and Local Identity in Uzbekistan tourism industry.

The mixed-methods approach described will offer a strong and comprehensive knowledge of the role that Tourism and Local Identity in Uzbekistan's tourism sector. This study aims to reflect the several effects of Tourism and Local Identity in Uzbekistan on tourism by integrating statistical surveys with qualitative interviews. Combining historical, cultural, and modern viewpoints will provide insightful analysis of how Uzbekistan may use its tourism and local identity to boost tourism while tackling issues of sustainability and globalization.

The collected data was exported from Google Forms into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) with a help of descriptive statistics analysis. Charts, graphs, and tables were generated to visualize patterns in age distribution, location, and perceptions of tourism's cultural influence.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The findings are interpreted with reference to relevant literature, and the implications for sustainable development of tourism and cultural preservation also discussed. The largest portion respondents within the

18-25 age group (42%) compare to under 18 years old group members (24%). Moreover, 18% of participants between 26 and 35 years old. Only 12% of people between 36-50 age groups. It means that, most of the active age group member were young age group of individuals.

The majority of participants 66% are female while 24% identified as male. Only 10% of participants chose the option “prefer not to say”. This suggests that women made up the largest group of participants in this survey. As a result, most active gender was females compare to males.

The status of respondents and the majority of them local resident 64%. Additionally, 14% of participants are foreign citizens. Also, 22% of respondents are international tourists, while 14% of respondents are domestic tourists. These results show that local participants were predominant.

58% of respondents were students, compare to 16% of government employees. Moreover, 14% of participants were from tourism sphere who worked as tour operators and guides. Also, 10% of respondents were artisan and craftspeople.

The survey results uncover differing preferences among respondents in regard to strategies to protect local identity. The most popular strategies were the support of training programs for artisans and teaching tourists’ cultural sensitivity, both of which were favored by 40% of participants. This demonstrates strong support for building capacity and raising awareness. In contrast, only 16% supported the reduction of commercialization of traditions and the increase of management control over the heritage sites suggesting less enthusiasm for more institutional suppression, or controlling measures. Promoting community-based tourism received moderate support (26%), which indicates the perceived ability of such tourism to promote development while preserving cultural identity. All in all, the results of the survey highlight the need for more active and constructive approaches based on education to protect intangible cultural heritage.

In order to evaluate tourist motivations, participants were asked: “What is the purpose of your visit (for tourists only)?” (Figure-1). Results show that 28% of respondents visited for business purposes, while 26% came for cultural sightseeing. These results imply that both economic as well as cultural factors greatly impact the behavior of tourists. For adventure tourism, the percentage was 22%, and 20% stated that their purpose was to visit family or friends. Identification as local residents accounted for 2% as well as 2% offering vague or unclassified answers as the total. From a general perspective, the data shows business and cultural factors are primary motivations for tourists, followed by leisure and social factors (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Purpose of the visit

The bar chart illustrates how participants from different age groups perceived the statement about “Tourism sometimes changes traditional customs and performances to satisfy tourist expectations.” The answers are categorized by the level of agreement and segmented by age and groups. This result shows that this age group has a generally ambivalent or indecisive viewpoint. In addition, 4 people in the 26–35 age range agreed, three were neutral, and one strongly agreed, indicating greater variation in viewpoints. In contrast to younger classmates, this implies a little more positive viewpoint. With one to three replies per category, the responses from participants between the ages of 36 and 50 were evenly dispersed and did not indicate either strong agreement or dissent. There was a tendency toward agreement among respondents, with three

agreeing and two strongly agreeing, suggesting that they believe tourism does have an impact on customs. As a result, a most notable percentage of respondents, mainly younger adults, respond to remain neutral or moderately agree, suggesting the influence of sustainable tourism mainly on cultural traditions also, not perceived as universally advantage or disadvantage among all age groups (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Perceptions of tourism's impact on traditions by age group

The survey question “Local traditions and lifestyles have become commercialized due to tourism” received a total of 50 responses, with a 5-point Likert scale where:

- 1 - Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Neutral; 4 –Agree; 5 - Strongly Agree

This result suggests that a majority (74%) of participants perceive tourism as a driving force behind the commercialization of local cultural practices, like performances, crafts, clothing, and rituals. The lowest disagreement rate implies that this trend is widely recognized and may be considered a key impact of tourism development in the area studied. As a result, potential cultural trade-off, where financial benefits from sustainable tourism may be coming at the cost of authenticity and traditional values a point worth addressing in tourism planning and cultural preservation methods.

The survey question is that “How important is it to involve local communities in tourism decision-making” with a 5-point Likert scale, the result shows that majority of respondents strongly agree and agree about to improve the involvement of local communities in some kind of decision-making about tourism sphere. Also, bar chart shows the low disagreement about these ideas. As a result, authorities should improve this strategy to promote sustainable tourism in Uzbekistan (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Challenges associated with tourism growth

This bar chart below shows the result of that people think tourism has many negatives if it become promote in our country. Majority of people (42%) chose that if sustainable tourism increases in our country it can lead to increased prices for local goods and services. While another group of participants chose that it leads to loss

of authenticity in traditions (26%) and overcrowding at heritage sites (26%). Additionally, 24% of respondents said it can influence to commercialization of culture in Uzbekistan. Lastly, 10% of respondents mentioned about environmental degradation, which means visitors can affect to biodiversity and it can lead to environmental damage. Lastly, 22% of respondents said public infrastructure has improved, which means tourism has led to better facilities. These results show how tourism can affects Uzbekistan's economic and heritage sides. Results highlighted most negative impacts may come from increased prices for local goods and services which is difficult to manage especially for local people.

Moreover, to the structured survey questions, participants were given the opportunity to share their personal views on tourism and local identity in Uzbekistan. A total of 46 participants responded to this open-ended question: "Please share any additional thoughts about tourism and local identity in Uzbekistan."

As a result between the responses, only 36 were identified as highly relevant and thematically rich. These comments provide qualitative insight into how tourism is perceived to influence cultural identity, community pride, and heritage preservation. Key recurring themes included:

-Promotion of cultural heritage and pride:

Several participants mentioned that tourism helps local people feel proud of their culture and identity. One respondent stated, "I think tourism can make local people proud of their identity." While another remarked, "Tourism in Uzbekistan helps preserve and promote local identity by showcasing its rich culture, traditions, and history."

-Value of historical cities and UNESCO sites:

Many highlighted the role of historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Tashkent more important region for tourism. For instance, one comment reads, "Uzbekistan's rich cultural heritage—Silk Road cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva—offers a strong sense of local identity."

-Encouragement of traditional crafts and local economies:

Only one participant mentioned about that "Tourism is strengthening local identity by encouraging traditional handicrafts, cultural pride, and protection of history." while other respondent wrote that, "It shows the world our identity and supports local communities," noted respondent.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This study explored the nuanced relationship between tourism development and regional identity in Uzbekistan, a country emerging as a prominent cultural destination in Central Asia. Through a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the research revealed that while tourism can serve as a vehicle for cultural preservation, it also poses risks of commodification and authenticity loss.

Findings indicate that a significant portion of respondents—particularly younger adults—hold ambivalent views regarding tourism's impact on traditional customs. While some recognize the positive role of tourism in promoting cultural pride and heritage, others express concern about rising prices, overcrowding, and the commercialization of traditions. Notably, the majority of participants strongly supported community involvement in tourism decision-making, emphasizing the need for more inclusive governance in shaping the future of the sector.

In light of these findings, several suggestions can be made to foster sustainable tourism and preserve local identity in Uzbekistan:

Promote community-based tourism models that empower local residents to actively participate in tourism planning and benefit from its outcomes.

Integrate cultural education programs for both tourists and local stakeholders to raise awareness about the value of intangible cultural heritage.

Develop regulatory mechanisms that limit the over-commercialization of traditional practices and promote authenticity in tourism offerings.

Support artisans and traditional craft producers through targeted training programs, fair trade networks, and market access initiatives.

Improve infrastructure and pricing policies to ensure that tourism-induced inflation does not adversely affect local populations.

Encourage participatory policy-making by regularly engaging communities in discussions about tourism development, its opportunities, and potential threats.

Overall, tourism in Uzbekistan holds substantial potential to drive economic and cultural revitalization. However, its development must be managed carefully to ensure that growth does not come at the expense of the country's rich cultural identity. By prioritizing sustainability, inclusion, and authenticity, Uzbekistan can position itself as a model for culturally responsible tourism in the region.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 5

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Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
